

Bacteria found in biofilm community and on aplysia

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Abstract

Marine bacteria are largely unexplored and represent a tremendous source for natural products with potential applications. Biofilm is a microbial community with a variety of microbes but have not been well studied. Sea hares are mollusks famous for their rich chemical weapons. In this study, I isolated bacteria from biofilm samples collected from Dasha River and the sea hare *Phidiana militaris*. After multiple rounds of purification and DNA sequencing, bacterial species including *Pseudoalteromonas piscicida*, *Vibrio neptunius*, *Vibrio harveyi*, *Pseudoalteromonas galathea*, *Pseudoalteromonas* sp., *Lysobacter xinjiangensis*, *Micrococcus luteus*, *Streptomyces fumigatiscleroticus*, *Ralstonia insidiosa*, *Skermanella aerolata*, *Nocardia rosealba*, *Agrobacterium fabrum*, *Brucella cytisi*, *Mesorhizobium sediminum*, *Paenibacillus cineris*, *Dyadobacter fermentans*, *Providencia vermicola*, *Brevibacillus formosus*, *Bosea thiooxidans*, and *Micromonospora wenchangensis* were isolated. The anti-pathogenic bioactivity of these bacterial strains was examined by anti-bacteria bioassay experiment, from which *Dyadobacter fermentans* and *Agrobacterium fabrum* were found to possess major bioactivity, suggesting potential of novel natural chemical compounds.

1. Introduction

Marine organisms, as a vital source of natural products, have vast potential in medicinal field as their secondary metabolites are proven to be valuable, and could be used as drug in curing infectious diseases resulting from pathogenic organisms [1] or for cancer treatments [2]. For instance, the natural products isolated from marine sessile organisms are also proven to be promising for anticancer treatments due to their biological synthesizing abilities [3]. However, it is suggested that about 91% of marine species are yet to be identified.

Sea hare, a kind of marine snail with a look similar to sea slug, is targeted in this study for discovery of natural product due to its distinctive anti-predator chemical defense strategy [4]. This chemical defense ability is en-

dowed by the bacteria adhering on the sea hares that allows them to accomplish anti-predatory purposes [5]. Therefore, hoping to extract medically and chemically valuable secondary metabolites, I captured the sea hare *Phidiana militaris* and isolated bacteria from *Phidiana militaris*, among which some might help their hosts to keep their predators away. Chemical compounds from these bacterial isolates were extracted to test for bioactivities.

Apart from isolating bacteria from the sea hare, I also use biofilm samples for this study considering the diversity of microbes in the biofilm community. Biofilm, a microbial community with remarkable microbial biodiversity since there are three distinct stages of biofilm formation, each consisting of different microbes [6].

This study used the biofilm samples collected in Dasha River together with the sea hare sample captured in Qixing Bay, after multiple rounds of purification and DNA sequencing, I isolated 23 distinct bacterial species, with ten *Proteobacteria*, four *Actinobacteria*, two *Firmicutes*, one *Bacteroidetes*, and three *Pseudomonadota*.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Collection of samples

Biofilm samples were collected from Dasha River (22°34'04.3"N 114°31'52.2"E) located in Guangdong, China. The biofilm samples were manually collected by gathering two fishing ropes and the seawater from the chosen site. The fresh samples were kept in a waterproof box which was then sent to the laboratory. The sea hare sample was collected in Qixing Bay. The sea hare sample was then dissected into fragments, including its head, main body, back, and tail.

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2.2. Extraction of bacteria in the samples

Bacteria were extracted in the laboratory by using the spreading rods to scrape off the microbes adhered to the fishing rope, as well as by dipping the spreading rod into the seawater to collect the microbes. The spreading rods with microbes adhering to them were then used for later spreading and streaking procedures. For the sea hare, different body parts were homogenized in 0.9% NaCl solution. The homogenates were then serially diluted, from 10x dilution to 1000x dilution using 0.9% NaCl solution.

2.3. Spreading and streaking

After collecting the microbes in the biofilm samples, spreading rods were used to spread the samples onto the R2A culture media (Difco™ R2A Agar) from Becton Dickinson Difco™ (The United States). Six culture plates were produced from biofilm samples with three samples collected from the fishing rope and the other three collected from the seawater. The samples were incubated in the incubator at a temperature of 37 °C for 48 hours. Each plate was observed under the microscope to see whether there were colonies with distinct features. Bacterial colonies with distinct characteristics were then purified by the streak plates method. Colonies with red, yellow, orange, white and grey colors, and with shapes like snowflakes and thin sheets were identified and then purified. The sea hare samples were spread on Marine Agar (MA) and R2A culture media. Colonies with distinct shapes and colors were produced, with predominantly circular, though with few exceptions forming crateriform elevation and undulate margins. Pink, black, yellow, beige colonies were found on the culture plates. Bacteria were purified using a positive displacement pipette with 10 µL micro tips. The tip was dipped into the colony and then used to streak the microbes onto the culture plate with R2A culture media. The streak method was repeated twice to ensure pure colonies were produced. Twenty-seven culture plates with purified bacteria were produced.

2.4. DNA extraction

The water bath method, in which the bacterial solution was boiled, was used for DNA extraction. A positive displacement pipette with a 10 µL micro tip was dipped into the single bacterial colony to collect the specific bacteria. The pipette was then dipped with bacteria on the tip into the 30 µL NaCl solution (0.9% NaCl and 99.1% double distilled water) in the 50 µL centrifuge tube. As 27 bacteria were isolated in previous step, 27 centrifuge tubes were used with one for each bacterium. These centrifuge tubes were first centrifuged for 20 seconds and then placed in the water bath floating racks, boiled in the thermostat water bath at 100°C temperature for 10 minutes.

2.5. Running PCR

The water bath floating rack with 27 centrifuge tubes was taken out for PCR test preparation. The solution used for the PCR test included 2 µL of each DNA primer 8F (5'-AGAGTTTGATCCTGGCTCA-3') and 1942R (5'-GGTTACCTTGTTACGACTT-3'), 25 µL of Taq polymerase, 20 µL of double distilled water and 1 µL of DNA solution. A solution was made for each bacterium. Set the PCR machine to run a program including steps of 95°C for three minutes, followed by a cycle repeated 32 times that includes 30 seconds with a temperature of 95°C, 30 seconds with 60°C and 20 seconds with 72°C. The cycle was then followed by 8 minutes of 72°C, and the PCR test ended with 4°C for solution preservation.

2.6. Electrophoresis test

The solutions were then examined by gel electrophoresis to determine if DNA was successfully extracted from the previous steps. The preparation for the gel test includes materials like agarose, TAE buffer and nucleic acid dye. Twenty grams of agarose were added to the solution of 25 mL of TAE buffer and 1.25 µL of nucleic acid dye. The solution was then poured into the agarose gel mold for 30 minutes to form a solid gel. After the gel had been solidified, 1 µL of loading buffer was placed onto a plate for each bacterium, and 5 µL of each DNA solution was then mixed with the loading buffer. Each mixture was then injected into a single rectangular dent in the gel, with one dent loaded with 3 µL of DNA marker. The gel was then placed in the two-dimensional gel electrophoresis machine for 15 minutes with 110 V of voltage.

2.7. Transmission electron microscopy

The phages were then morphologically analyzed through TEM. 20 µL of desalinated phage solution was dropped onto carbon-coated copper grids, which were stored in a dark area for 30 minutes to allow absorption of the solution. In order to view the phages, the sample was negatively stained using 1% phosphotungstic acid for 1 minute, and then allowed to air dry for 10 minutes, after which TEM phage images were taken, and phage size was measured. The device used was a Hitachi TEM system, set to 80 kV, and particle size was measured from at least 5 particles using ImageJ software (Schneider et al., 2012).

2.8. DNA sequencing

The 27 tubes of solution made for the PCR test were then sent to Guangzhou Rubio Biotechnology Co., Ltd. for DNA Sanger sequencing using an ABI 3730XL DNA analyzer.

2.9. Making seed culture fluid

SGTYP (SG) culture media was used for culturing the seed culture fluid for the bacteria identified earlier, *Pseu-*

doalteromonas piscicida, *Vibrio neptunius*, *Vibrio harveyi*, *Pseudoalteromonas galathea*, *Pseudoalteromonas* sp., *Lysobacter xinjiangensis*, *Micrococcus luteus*, *Streptomyces fumigatiscleroticus*, *Ralstonia insidiosa*, *Skermanella aerolata*, *Nocardia rosealba*, *Agrobacterium fabrum*, *Brucella cytisi*, *Mesorhizobium sediminum*, *Paenibacillus cineris*, *Dyadobacter fermentans*, *Providencia vermicola*, *Brevibacillus formosus*, *Bosea thiooxidans*, and *Micromonospora wenchangensis*. 10 mL of the culture media was first added to the 50 mL centrifuge tube, and then the bacteria were scraped off from the culture plate and added to the centrifuge tube. The centrifuge tubes with SG culture media and bacteria were then put to the shaker with temperature of 28°C, speed of 200 rpm, for 24 hours. The centrifuge tubes were then taken out from the shaker, followed by the step of adding the seed culture fluid from each centrifuge tube to the 200 mL SG culture media, contained in a 1000 mL flask. These flasks were then put to the shaker with temperature of 28°C, speed of 200 rpm, for three days.

2.10. Crude extract preparation

Four hundred milliliters of ethyl acetate were added to the seed 200 mL culture fluid contained in the separatory funnel in order to separate the organic phase and the aqueous phase. After 15 minutes of waiting, the organic phase and aqueous phase were separated. The valve was then turned on to release the organic phase. The remained aqueous phase was then put on the rotary evaporator in order to extract the compounds in the solution. The compounds were extracted when the ethyl acetate is evaporated, leaving only the needed compounds in the separatory funnel. 500 μ L of dimethyl sulfoxide was then added into each separatory funnel. The solution was taken out and put into the 1.5 mL centrifuge tube.

2.11. Bioactivity test

Three pathogenic bacteria, *Methicillin-resistant Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) *Acinetobacter baumannii*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* were cultured in the laboratory and prepared to test the bioactivity of the isolated bacteria. These bacteria were diluted to 1/1000 concentration. Two types of culture plates were used, the circular one and the square-shaped one with larger volume. The circular culture plates were split into six even parts, and the square-shaped ones were split into nine even parts. Each part was inoculated with one of the three pathogenic bacteria species or DMSO. These bacteria were evenly spread onto the MH Broth in the culture plate, 2 plates were produced for each bacterium. Then, filter was cut to 1 mm diameter of circular pieces, which were then places in each part of the culture plate. 15 μ L of the extracts from *Pseudoalteromonas piscicida*, *Vibrio neptunius*, *Vibrio harveyi*, *Pseudoalteromonas galathea*, *Pseudoalteromonas* sp., *Lysobacter xinjiangensis*, *Micrococcus lu-*

teus, *Streptomyces fumigatiscleroticus*, *Ralstonia insidiosa*, *Skermanella aerolata*, *Nocardia rosealba*, *Agrobacterium fabrum*, *Brucella cytisi*, *Mesorhizobium sediminum*, *Paenibacillus cineris*, *Dyadobacter fermentans*, *Providencia vermicola*, *Brevibacillus formosus*, *Bosea thiooxidans*, and *Micromonospora wenchangensis*, as well as pure DMSO, were placed onto each piece of filter paper. The procedure was repeated the twice, using 5 μ L of the extracts. The culture plates were then placed into the incubator for 16 hours.

3. Results

3.1. Bacteria isolated from biofilm samples

Bacteria with various distinct features appeared on the culture plates. PCR and the gel electrophoresis were used to test whether DNA were extracted for latter DNA sequencing. For bacteria isolated from the biofilm sample, DNA from 7 bacteria out of total of 10 were extracted, leaving Huipian and Da-o, with the rest all around 1000bp, shown in the gel test result (Figure 1). These bacteria then underwent DNA sequencing and then identified as *Pseudoalteromonas piscicida*, *Vibrio neptunius*, *Vibrio harveyi*, *Pseudoalteromonas galathea* and *Pseudoalteromonas* sp. Genus *Vibrio* was dominant on the culture plates since genus *Vibrio* is proven to be one of the pioneering and dominant genus in biofilm formation [7]. Bacteria with vivid color, red (Figure 2a) and yellow (Figure 2b), were identified as genus *Pseudoalteromonas*.

Figure 1. The gel from the electrophoresis test for isolates of biofilm samples.

3.2. Species *Vibrio neptunius* has four distinct forms

Four out of ten isolates were tested to be the same species, *Vibrio neptunius*, though with different colony morphologies in the culture plates. One of them exhibits

Figure 2. Bacteria isolated from biofilm samples. **a.** Purified bacteria of species *Pseudoalteromonas* sp.; **b.** Purified bacteria of species *Pseudoalteromonas piscicida*.

a colony morphology of a tiny circular shape, with grey color (Figure 3a), whereas the other two of them were with medium-sized circular colonies, yet one of them (Figure 3b) can better reflect lights than the other two. Moreover, one of them (Figure 3c) has a creamy-white color while the other (Figure 3d & e) is mainly translucent and with a visible nucleus-like structure.

3.3. Bacteria found in sea hare samples

Two major phyla of bacteria were isolated from sea hare samples: proteobacteria and actinobacteria. These bacteria generally formed medium-sized, round colonies. Several exceptions were found, either with vivid colors or with special shapes. For example, the species *Lysobacter xinjiangensis*, *Micrococcus luteus*, and *Providencia vermicola* produces yellow pigments. Species *Ralstonia insidiosa* also produced pigments in its colonies, forming red, round colonies. The one with the most special color and shape was species *Nocardia rosealba*, producing pale orange and pink colonies with volcano-like shape. Another exception was *Micromonospora wenchangensis*, producing brown, ivory, and yellow colonies. Though the species *Brevibacillus formosus* had white and beige colors for its colonies, it has frosted surfaces of colonies. From sea hares, bacteria with a variety of morphologies were isolated.

3.4. Bioactivity test

All bacteria from the biofilm samples exhibit no bioactivity to *Acinetobacter baumannii* (Figure 4a) and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (Figure 4g), leaving no zones of inhibition. However, species *Pseudoalteromonas galathea* and *Pseudoalteromonas* sp. exhibited bioactivity towards pathogenic bacteria MRSA, with the zones of inhibition with radius of 1mm and 0.7mm, respectively (Figure 4b). For the bacteria isolated from the sea hare samples, they exhibit significantly more bioactivity against *Acinetobacter baumannii*, MRSA, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. For *Acinetobacter baumannii*, species *Bosea thiooxidans* (labeled 2H2) exhibits bioactivity, with the zone of inhibition with radius of 1 mm (Figure 4d). Species *Agrobacterium fabrum* (H93), *Brucella cytisi* (H114), and *Lysobacter xinjiangensis* (H32), exhibits bioactivity against it, with

the zone of inhibition with radius of 2 mm, 1.1 mm, and 2mm, respectively (Figure 4.h). For *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, several bacteria isolated from sea hare samples also show bioactivity against it. Species *Dyadobacter fermentans* (H130), *Providencia vermicola* (H167), *Micromonospora wenchangensis* (2H6), *Agrobacterium fabrum* (H93), *Brucella cytisi* (H114), *Lysobacter xinjiangensis* (H32), *Streptomyces fumigatiscleroticus* (H47A), and *Paenibacillus cineris* (H128) exhibits bioactivity against it, having the zone of inhibition with radius of 1 mm, 0.9 mm, 1.5 mm, 1.2 mm, 0.5 mm, 1 mm, 1 mm, and 1.9 mm, respectively (Figure 4e & 4f). For MRSA, species *Dyadobacter fermentans* (H130), *Providencia vermicola* (H167), and *Micromonospora wenchangensis* (2H6) exhibits bioactivity against it, with zone of inhibition with radius of 2 mm, 0.6 mm, and 2 mm, respectively (Figure 4c).

4. Discussion

4.1. Bacterial interaction in biofilm community

Many bacteria isolated in this study were identified as the genus *Vibrio*. Four out of ten bacteria were identified as *Vibrio neptunius*. *Vibrio neptunius* could have appeared in biofilm samples since they generally present and cause diseases in marine bivalves [8]. Moreover, another species, *Vibrio harveyi*, was also extracted from the biofilm sample. *Vibrio harveyi* specializes in biofilm formation, which makes it the most common species in biofilm sample [9]. As to the species *Pseudoalteromonas piscicida*, it specializes in killing *Vibrio*, which might explain why *Pseudoalteromonas piscicida* also presents in the biofilm samples. The genus *Pseudoalteromonas*, hosting over forty species, has numerous species that produce antimicrobial metabolites [10], which therefore gives it the potential for anti-biofilm usage. Apart from its antimicrobial ability, its ability to adapt to extreme environments, including places with extreme temperatures and deep in the ocean [11], also gives clues to its ubiquity.

4.2. Medical potential of bacteria in sea hares

A large number of the bacterial species found in sea hare samples have profound medical potentials. The phylum Proteobacteria has been long regarded as a valuable source of compounds for anti-cancer and anti-dementia usage (Buijs et al., 2019). Specific genus of marine bacteria also provides promising medical prospects. For instance, species *Micromonospora wenchangensis*, belonging to the genus *Micromonospora*, have great therapeutic potential. The second metabolites derived from *Micromonospora* enrich the chemical diversity of natural products, thus making the genus particularly promising for pharmaceutical usage [6]. Moreover, from the same genus *Micromonospora*, compounds with anti-cancer potentials were also extracted, proving the medical potential of the entire genus [12].

Figure 3. Different colony morphologies of the species *Vibrio neptunius*. **a.** an isolate colony morphology of a tiny circular shape, with grey color; **b.** an isolate with medium-sized circular colonies; **c.** an isolate with creamy-white color colonies; **d, e.** isolate colonies with translucent and with a visible nucleus-like structure.

Figure 4. Results of bioactivity test of the isolated bacteria against pathogenic bacteria.

Moreover, *Streptomyces* species are also proven to have great medical potentials with their second metabolites [13]. Species *Streptomyces fumigatiscleroticus*, isolated from the sea hare samples, is also proven to be a source for antibiotics, again reinforcing the pharmaceutical significance of these marine bacteria (Wang et al., 2020). In addition to the medical potential given by their metabolites, some genera and species can provide protection against root-rot diseases of medicinal plants. For example, the species *Brevibacillus*

lus formosus, a species isolated in this study, is proven to prevent root-rot diseases of *Panax notoginseng*, a traditional medicinal plant (Li et al., 2021). Likewise, the genus *Paenibacillus* is very useful for antimicrobial and insecticide productions, as well as preventing insect herbivores and phytopathogens [14].

4.3. Aversive impacts of bacteria in sea hares

However, bacteria with aversive impacts, causing diseases and economic loss, were also isolated from sea hare samples. For instance, the genus *Brucella* usually leads to infertility among food animals, leading to economic loss in the food sector worldwide. The genus *Brucella* also causes brucellosis among humans, leading to undulant fevers [15]. Moreover, the genus *Nocardia* causes a wide range of diseases among humans, with each species having variable drug susceptibility, needing therefore particularly large amount of research [16].

4.4. Future prospects

While most of the bacteria had no astonishing anti-pathogenic bioactivity, some of them worth future investigation to tap their potential. For instance, species *Dyadobacter fermentans* (H130) and *Agrobacterium fabrum* (H93) exhibit relatively strong bioactivity against both pathogens MRSA and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, thus showing their

potential in anti-pathogenic functions. Apart from anti-pathogenic usage, the bacterial species isolated from the sea hare samples also have promising medical and pharmaceutical potentials, therefore needing future research and application in medical fields.

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